

Impact of *Aspergillus niger* AN27 on growth promotion and sheath blight disease reduction in rice

J. Kandhari, S. Majumder, and B. Sen, Division of Plant Pathology, Indian Agricultural Research Institute (IARI), New Delhi 110012, India

Sheath blight caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn is a threat to rice cultivation in different agroclimatic conditions. Many bacteria and fungi from rice field soils are antagonistic to *R. solani* (Gogoi and Roy 1993, Roy 1984, 1993, Sen et al 1993).

We tested the ability of *Aspergillus niger* AN27 and its bioformulation to suppress sheath blight. Seeds of Pusa Basmati 1 were planted in four nursery trays (650 seeds tray⁻¹). Seeds of one tray were treated with the bioformulation *Kalisena* SD at 4 g kg⁻¹ before planting. Untreated seeds were sown in the other three trays. At transplanting, root and shoot length of plants and biomass were measured for each treatment. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 15 × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with four treatments. Three replications of two 3-m rows were maintained. Standard agronomic practices were followed. The experiment was conducted for two continuous crop years (1997 and 1998). Plants were inoculated with a virulent isolate of *R. solani* by placing two colonized typha bits

(Bhaktavatsalam et al 1978) in the center tillers of each hill at 40 d after transplanting (maximum tillering). At 45 d after inoculation, number of total tillers, infected tillers, effective tillers, lesion height, and disease reduction were measured.

The 1997 and 1998 results were similar and were thus averaged. Plants raised from treated seeds (PTS) were significantly more vigorous, showing an increase of 6.5 and 10.0 cm in root and shoot length, respectively, and 100% heavier biomass than the untreated seedlings at transplanting (Table 1). In the field, PTS had significantly more tillers per plant and a higher percentage of effective tillers (Table 1). There was a 32.9% disease reduction in PTS; in the spray treatment of *A. niger* AN27, reduction was only 12.2%. Average lesion height was also reduced up to 14.5% in PTS (Table 2).

These results indicate that resistance to sheath blight is induced in rice by the biocontrol agent *A. niger* AN27 and its bioformulation *Kalisena* SD. Roy (1993) reported that infection of sheath blight

could be reduced by adding *A. terreus* in potted plants. The cellulolytic activity of *R. solani*, however, could not be reduced. Reduction of *R. solani* by *A. terreus*, particularly when plants are treated before inoculation with sclerotia of the pathogen, was reported by Gogoi and Roy (1993). Sen et al (1993) found that *A. niger*, isolated from the rhizosphere of a healthy muskmelon plant adjacent to wilted areas, proved to be an effective biocontrol agent against *R. solani* by way of antibiosis, overgrowth, and hyperparasitism. *Kalisena* SD, developed by IARI, has been launched in the market to control soil-borne plant pathogens and to promote plant growth.

References

- Bhaktavatsalam G, Satyanarayana K, Reddy APK, Johri VT. 1978. Evaluation of sheath blight resistance in rice. *Int. Rice Res. Notes* 3(3):9–10.
- Gogoi R, Roy AK. 1993. Effect of foliar spraying of *Aspergillus terreus* on sheath blight and rice plant characteristics. *Int. Rice Res. Notes* 18(3):31–32.

Table 1. Impact of *Aspergillus niger* AN27 and its bioformulation *Kalisena* SD on growth of rice cv Pusa Basmati I inoculated with *Rhizoctonia solani*.

Treatment	Transplant			Tillers	
	Root length (cm) Av of 20	Shoot length (cm) Av of 20	Biomass (g) Av of 100	Total no. plant ⁻¹	Percent effective
Seed dressing <i>Kalisena</i> SD	13.4	40.0	60.0	11.4	93.7 (75.75) ^a
Sheath spray <i>A. niger</i> AN27	6.9	29.9	30.3	9.5	83.2 (65.80)
Untreated, inoculated	6.9	29.9	30.0	8.8	76.6 (61.09)
Untreated, uninoculated	6.9	30.0	30.0	8.8	76.1 (60.46)
CD at <i>P</i> = 0.05				1.17	3.46

^aNumbers in parentheses are arcsine-transformed values.

Table 2. Effect of *A. niger* AN27 and its bioformulation *Kalisena* SD on sheath blight of rice.

Treatment	Infected tillers (%)	Disease reduction over control (%)	Lesion height (%)
Seed dressing	63.7	32.9	66.7
<i>Kalisena</i> SD	(52.95) ^a	(34.87)	(54.76)
Sheath spray	83.8	12.2	72.3
<i>A. niger</i> AN27	(66.28)	(20.32)	(58.24)
Untreated, inoculated	98.0	0.0	81.2
	(78.62)	(4.05)	(64.32)
Untreated, uninoculated	0.0	0.0	—
	(4.05)	(4.05)	(4.05)
CD at <i>P</i> = 0.05	3.14	3.30	2.09

^aNumbers in parentheses are arcsine-transformed values.

Roy AK. 1984. Inhibitory effect of *Aspergillus terreus* Thom. against *Rhizoctonia solani* f. sp. *sasaki*. Int. Rice Res. Notes 9(3):13.

Roy AK. 1993. Sheath blight of rice in India. Indian Phytopathol. 46(3):197–205.

Sen B, Sharma J, Asalmol MN, Chattopadhyay C, Patibanda AK. 1993. *Aspergillus niger*—a potential biocontrol agent for soil-borne pathogens. Indian Phytopathol. 46(3):275.

.....

Influence of rice varieties on parasitism of the African rice gall midge (AfRGM)

F.E. Nwilene, M.P. Jones, and O. Okhidievbie, West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA), 01 BP 2551, Bouaké 01, Côte d'Ivoire E-mail: f.nwilene@cgiar.org

The African rice gall midge (AfRGM), *Orseolia oryzivora* Harris & Gagné (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae), is a major constraint to rainfed and irrigated lowland rice production in Africa. The most common natural enemies associated with AfRGM are the polyembryonic endoparasitoid *Platygaster diplosisae* Risbec (Hymenoptera: Platygasteridae) and the solitary ectoparasitoid *Aprostocetus procerae* Risbec (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae). These species have potential as biological control agents against AfRGM (Williams et al 1997). The extent to which the activity of these parasitoids may be influenced by rice genotype is not well known. This is a crucial issue because the effects of resistance factor(s) in the rice genotype on the developing midge larvae are likely to be exhibited on the next trophic level of association, i.e., on the AfRGM parasitoids. Such interactions are known to exist in maize, sorghum, and other crops (Potting et al 1995, Nwanze and Nwilene 1998).

Some natural enemies are known to base their foraging strategies on plant volatiles that mediate searching behavior, especially at longer distances. Plant resistance to insects can result from antagonism due to the presence of chemicals in vari-

ous plant tissues. To optimize the benefits from integrating the breeding for resistance to AfRGM and biological control, it is desirable that these management options be either complementary or synergistic and not antagonistic.

A trial was carried out in 1998 at the Ebonyi State College of Agriculture greenhouse in the Ikwo local government area, near Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, southeast Nigeria. Ikwo is in the forest/savanna transition zone. The AfRGM and its parasitoids *P. diplosisae* and *A. procerae* were reared in seedboxes in the greenhouse (25–30 °C temperature and 50–90% relative humidity). The cultures had been maintained for 4 wk prior to the experiments. Four rice varieties showing different levels of resistance—ITA306 (susceptible), Cisadane (tolerant), NHTA8 (partially resistant), and Eguazankpa (widely grown traditional variety in the middle belt of Nigeria) (Williams et al 1997)—were used to determine whether these differences in resistance affected parasitism of *P. diplosisae* and *A. procerae*.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. About 80 seedlings in each seedbox were exposed to 10 gravid

female and 5 male AfRGM at 12 d after seeding. Two days after AfRGM infestation, twenty 1-d-old gravid females of *P. diplosisae* were released in each box. Two weeks after AfRGM infestation, when pupation commenced, twenty 1-d-old gravid females of *A. procerae* were released in each box. (Separate boxes were infested with *P. diplosisae* and *A. procerae*.) Four weeks after parasitoid introduction, 40 plants per box were dissected and data on the following were recorded: tillers with galls, total tillers, number of larvae/pupae collected from galls, number of larvae/pupae parasitized, and percent parasitism. Data were subjected to analysis of variance.

Under no-choice conditions, in the experiment with *A. procerae*, AfRGM infestation of partially resistant variety NHTA8 was significantly lower than that of ITA306 and Cisadane at 50 d after crop emergence (Fig. 1). In the experiment with *P. diplosisae*, however, the four varieties did not differ in levels of AfRGM infestation. There was no significant difference in the number of larvae/pupae parasitized, and percent parasitism by both parasitoids was also consistently high in the four varieties (see figure). Both parasitoids attacked almost every gall that was infested. The